

IMPACT OF MIGRATION PROCESSES ON HUMAN CAPITAL

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Abstract: this article is devoted to the impact of migration processes on human capital, migration of "golden heads" to foreign countries, going to study and the impact on the economy of other countries, the results of a survey of school graduates and young people. In addition, the article reveals the role and importance of education in the development of human capital.

Key words: human capital, education, youth, graduates, migration processes.

In the period of modern socio-economic development, it is impossible to build a competitive national economy without taking into account the international trends in the field of ensuring the quality of education, without taking into account effective strategic and practical measures. Although the reason is not fully understood, the quality of education in a country (including its duration) and sustainable economic growth are directly proportional to each other. Thus, quality education creates a basis for effective and continuous education of a person from the beginning to the end of his work. In addition, the level of primary education coverage among the population is a more accurate indicator of economic growth than the average literacy rate. It is difficult to define the concept of "quality of education" with a general, simple or standard expression, because it is a multifaceted and dynamic concept. Its meaning depends on who evaluates it, what criteria and indicators are used, what goals and perspectives are set, as well as the position of different social groups and participants of the educational process.

According to statistics, Uzbekistan is ranked 5th among the countries whose students study abroad. About 110,000 students are studying abroad. In the last 20 years, the number of people who went abroad to study has increased from 2.2 million to 6.39 million¹. It can be seen from the numbers that studying abroad is increasing more and more. It is necessary to study this situation objectively. Study abroad out of interest or dissatisfaction with the education system in the country. In this regard, it will be necessary to consider the need for research institutes, "think tanks" to work, and at the same time to further improve the quality of education.

Since the 1960s, various international research methods have been developed to compare the achievements of countries. Among these methods, the most cited studies are:

- An international survey on the literacy level of the elderly population jointly conducted by the Organization for Economic Development and Cooperation and Statistics Canada;
- Tests proficiency in reading, math, and science among 15-year-olds in selected countries around the world every three years. (PISA);
- Trends in learning every 4 years, which assesses the quality of mathematics and science education of students in 49 countries, First covering 35 countries in 2001 and next covering 45 countries per year in 2006, 4th grade students, the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study, PIRLS, among school teachers and administrators;
- International Assessment of Competencies among the Elderly, implemented by the OECD since 2011 (Program of International Assessment of Adult Competencies, PIAAC);
- Knowledge Assessment Methodology (KAM) used by the World Bank Institute. Knowledge Index (KI) and Knowledge Economic Index (KEI);
- The Education sub-index of the Human Development Index used in the UNDP's Global Human Development Reports.

¹ <https://data.uis.unesco.org/index.aspx?queryid=3807>

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing many projects to become one of the developed countries. The education system is always in the center of attention of the leader of our country as one of the priority directions.

The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Pre-School and School Education are the main bodies implementing the reforms, and in addition to the Ministry, other state bodies, international and local organizations are contributing to the implementation of the reforms.

The rapid development of the country's economy at the expense of means of income has stimulated continuous development in construction, infrastructure, banking and finance, education, health care, social security of the population, human development and other areas. In this period, more than ever, multifaceted state policy regarding education and youth is being carried out.

Along with the development of education, issues of socio-economic development of our country are being taken into account in the state programs related to education and youth. In addition to state programs, cooperation projects with international organizations are being implemented in order to increase the level of education, creating conditions for accelerating this process. One of the priority goals is to train young personnel with modern knowledge along with improving the quality of education within the framework of programs and projects.

Currently, new professions and new specialties are emerging around the world. Many of the professions that were important until now are disappearing. Some professions that existed 20 years ago no longer exist and will never exist. As we are in the period of the fourth industrial revolution, this process will continue without interruption. We are a country with a population of 38 million. Therefore, we need to create opportunities for our citizens, especially our youth, to acquire modern professions, and in the future, they should work continuously in those learned professions and it should bear fruit. Knowledge and literacy determine the prosperous future of young people. Human capital, intellectual capital, knowledge and skills become more powerful and inflexible when combined with love for the country and respect for our values. Therefore, what is required of today's youth is not to forget patriotism and our national moral values.

Human capital cannot be imagined without the knowledge and intelligence of young people. In order to develop human capital, it is necessary to direct young people to education from childhood. However, in some regions of the world, children are still not paid attention to their education, but are treated as labor force using their strength and work. However, they must first get an education and thereby contribute to the development of human capital in the future.

In May 2024, the "Institute of Macroeconomic and Territorial Studies" conducted a survey in order to study how responsibly parents approach their child's future and their participation in the educational process. 3,602 respondents from parents with different backgrounds and backgrounds took part in the survey. The result of the survey showed that 94.6% of parents talk to each other about their child's future, and 13.9% have different opinions. 97.8% of parents say that they talk with their child about his future profession and interests, and 2.2% do not talk about it at all. In addition, according to the results of the survey, 20.7% of young people are doctors, 18.2% are teachers, 15.0% are journalists, 10.5% are economists, 7.8% are IT specialists, 5.2% entrepreneur, 5.3% wanted to become a financier and 1% wanted to become a lawyer¹. 17.1 thousand out of more than 390 thousand graduates participated in the survey on the choice of profession among the graduates of the scientific-research institute named after Abdulla Avloni. According to the results of the survey, 67 percent of the respondents said that they have clearly chosen who they want to be in the future, and 11 percent said that they want to go to work abroad. 6 percent of respondents planned to start a family. In the question directly related to the fate of the graduates, when the graduates who are planning to go abroad for work were asked why they want to leave, 37% of them

¹ https://imrs.uz/archives/news/report_2024_05. Makroiqtisodiy va hududiy tadqiqotlar institutining 2024-yil may oyi faoliyatining asosiy ko'rsatgichlari

said that they want to leave because they are interested in studying, but do not have the financial means¹.

At every stage of human historical development, society has developed in an integral relationship with education. Raising the young generation is one of the oldest activities. Some societies may not be able to mobilize sufficient resources for educational activities and institutions. But all of them implicitly recognize the central role of education in social life. The importance of education is related to many factors. For example, when children take their first steps in life, they do not know how to read, write, count, they are obviously unaware of the moral standards and cultural achievements of the society they live in. Thanks to the efforts of school teachers and family education, as well as the possibilities of mass media and the Internet in modern times, the young generation is learning to read, write, and count. For several years, he studies the surrounding environment, moral and behavioral norms. People have different levels of knowledge and skills. Therefore, the educational system actually performs the task of social sorting and has a great impact on the future socio-economic status of individuals.

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¹ <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2022/06/11/sorovnoma-maktab-bitiruvchilarining-11-foizi-chet-elga-ishlashga-ketishni-rejalashtirgan>